

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Co(II) with Pyrocatechol Violet and Xylenol Orange as Primary and Amino Acids as Secondary Ligands

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The complexes of the type $K_2[KCo(PV)(AA)_2]$ and $K_2[KHCo(XO)(AA)]$, where PV and XO are deprotonated pyrocatechol violet and xylenol orange, respectively and AA=deprotonated hippuric acid, valine, alanine, aspartic acid and cysteine, were prepared in pure crystalline form, analysed chemically and characterised on the basis of IR and electronic spectra, conductance and magnetic measurements. The values of magnetic moment (4.46-4.59 B.M.), $10Dq$, B and β indicated their octahedral structure.

SURVEY of literature reveals that little information is available on the mixed ligand complexes of pyrocatechol violet (PV) and xylenol orange (XO) with metal ions. The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of Co(II) complexes of PV and XO and also of mixed ligand complexes containing PV and XO as primary and amino acids as secondary ligands.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions: PV and XO were purified by the well known method of Hisakuni *et al.*¹. All other chemicals were of A. R. quality.

Physical measurements: Magnetic moments were determined by the Gouy's method at room temperature. The diamagnetic corrections for the ligands and the metal ion under investigation were made using published data^{2,3}. Electronic spectra were run on a Carl Zeiss Specord UV-VIS spectrophotometer. Reflectance spectra were obtained with Carl Zeiss Specol spectrophotometer fitted with a reflectance attachment of type Rd/O. Electrical conductance was measured with a Systronics conductivity bridge, type 302. Absorbance measurements in the lower region were made on a Unicam, SP-500 spectrophotometer and IR spectra were run on Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer.

Preparation of the complexes: The simple complexes were prepared by mixing the aqueous solutions (0.01 M) of cobalt(II) and dye in the ratio of 1 : 1. The pH of the mixture was raised to ≈ 11 by the addition of KOH and the mixture refluxed on water bath for 1 hr. Acetone was then added to the cold solution till shining pink crystals were formed.

The mixed ligand complexes were also similarly prepared by adding two fold excess of amino acid

in the mixture of Co(II) and PV (1 : 1) and one equivalent of amino acid in the mixture of Co(II) and XO (1 : 1). The mixture was concentrated by evaporation and then cooled in ice. Acetone was then added to obtain the pink crystals.

Results and Discussion

The results of analysis for metal, C, H, S and N and of molar conductances of aqueous solutions of simple and mixed ligand complexes are given in Table 1.

IR studies: IR spectra of the isolated complexes were taken in KBr medium, by the method of slow scanning in the IR region. The stretching bands of the ligands and their respective metal complexes are given in Table 2. A strong band at 3600 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of PV and XO because of phenolic -OH disappeared in the spectra of metal complexes indicating thereby the coordination of metals through phenolic oxygen atom. The bands at 3350 and 970 cm^{-1} were obtained in the case of simple complexes which indicated the presence of water molecules inside the coordination sphere. The characteristic bands because of antisymmetric and symmetric COO^- groups were obtained in the region $1620-1640$ and $1390-1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, showing the presence of coordinated carboxyl group. An additional band at 720 cm^{-1} in the spectra of XO complexes was due to the presence of uncoordinated COOH group. The stretching band obtained at 3300 cm^{-1} indicated the coordination of amino group. The bands due to $-\text{SO}_3$, $\text{M}-\text{N}$ and $\text{M}-\text{O}$ were obtained at 1020 , $410-480$ and $370-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively.

Electronic spectra and magnetic studies of the complexes: The observed values of magnetic moment lie in the range 4.46-4.59 B.M. (Table 3)

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Complexes	Analysis % ; (Calcd.) Found					Molar conductivity
		M	O	H	S	N	
1.	$K_2[Co(C_{10}H_{10}O_7S)(H_2O)_4]$	(9.98) 9.90	(38.58) 38.19	(3.04) 3.07	(5.40) 5.15	—	250
2.	$K_2[KCo(C_{10}H_{10}O_7S)(C_2H_5O_2N)_2]$	(6.19) 6.14	(46.58) 46.12	(2.72) 2.74	(3.35) 3.32	(2.99) 2.91	405
3.	$K_2[KCo(C_{10}H_{10}O_7S)(C_2H_5O_2N)_2]$	(7.11) 7.04	(41.97) 41.55	(3.61) 3.58	(3.85) 3.81	(3.37) 3.33	400
4.	$K_2[KCo(C_{10}H_{10}O_7S)(C_2H_5O_2N)_2]$	(7.63) 7.56	(38.80) 38.42	(2.64) 2.87	(4.13) 3.89	(3.62) 3.59	405
5.	$K_2[KCo(C_{10}H_{10}O_7S)(C_2H_5O_2N)_2]$	(6.85) 6.80	(37.68) 37.24	(2.55) 2.58	(3.71) 3.67	(3.25) 3.22	400
6.	$K_2[KCo(C_{10}H_{10}O_7S)(C_2H_7O_2NS)_2]$	(7.03) 6.97	(35.75) 35.37	(2.86) 2.83	(11.43) 11.32	(3.33) 3.30	410
7.	$K_2[KCo(C_{10}H_{10}O_7S)(H_2O)_4]$	(6.03) 6.36	(40.56) 40.15	(3.27) 3.30	(3.48) 3.45	(3.05) 3.02	408
8.	$K_2[KHCo(C_{10}H_{10}O_7S)(C_2H_5O_2N)_2]$	(5.55) 5.50	(45.27) 44.78	(3.30) 3.24	(3.02) 2.99	(3.96) 3.92	405
9.	$K_2[KHCo(C_{10}H_{10}O_7S)(C_2H_5O_2N)_2]$	(5.89) 5.83	(43.27) 42.80	(3.70) 3.74	(3.20) 3.17	(4.20) 4.16	410
10.	$K_2[KHCo(C_{10}H_{10}O_7S)(C_2H_5O_2N)_2]$	(5.85) 5.80	(40.47) 40.10	(3.17) 3.20	(3.28) 3.25	(4.32) 4.27	408
11.	$K_2[KHCo(C_{10}H_{10}O_7S)(C_2H_5O_2N)_2]$	(5.60) 5.56	(39.92) 39.53	(3.04) 3.01	(3.15) 3.12	(4.14) 4.10	411
12.	$K_2[KHCo(C_{10}H_{10}O_7S)(C_2H_7O_2NS)_2]$	(5.66) 5.61	(39.19) 38.83	(3.17) 3.20	(6.37) 6.30	(4.18) 4.13	420

$C_{10}H_{10}O_7S$ = deprotonated PV ;

$C_{10}H_{10}O_7N_2S$ = deprotonated XO ;

$C_2H_5O_2N$, $C_2H_5O_2NS$, $C_2H_5O_2N$, $C_2H_5O_2N$, $C_2H_5O_2N$ and $C_2H_7O_2NS$ are deprotonated hippuric acid, valine, alanine, aspartic acid and cysteine, respectively.

TABLE 2—TENTATIVE ASSIGNMENTS OF SIGNIFICANT PEAKS IN THE INFRA RED SPECTRA OF METAL COMPLEXES

Complex no.	ν_{OH} (phenolic)	ν_{H_2O}	ν_{NH}	$\nu_{C=O}$	ν_{COO^-} antisymmetric	ν_{COO^-} symmetric	ν_{SO_2}	ν_{M-N}	ν_{M-O}
PV	3600(s)	—	—	1610(s)	—	—	1020(s)	—	—
XO	3600(s)	—	—	1610(s)	1720(s) 1590(s)	—	1020(s)	—	—
1.	—	3350(b) 965(w)	—	1610(s)	—	—	1020(s)	—	380(w)
2.	—	—	3300(b)	1610(s)	1640(s)	1400(s)	1020(s)	405(w)	370(w)
3.	—	—	3300(b)	1610(s)	1620(s)	1390(s)	1020(s)	480(w)	390(w)
4.	—	—	3350(b)	1610(s)	1620(s)	1390(s)	1020(s)	460(w)	400(w)
5.	—	—	3290(b)	1610(s)	1640(s)	1400(s)	1020(s)	420(w)	390(w)
6.	—	—	3300(b)	1610(s)	1640(s)	1400(s)	1020(s)	410(w)	380(w)
7.	—	3350(b) 970(w)	—	1615(s)	1720(s) 1640(s)	1400(s)	1030(s)	410(w)	390(w)
8.	—	—	3300(b)	1610(s)	1640(s)	1400(s)	1020(s)	410(w)	380(w)
9.	—	—	3300(b)	1610(s)	1630(s)	1390(s)	1020(s)	450(w)	400(w)
10.	—	—	3290(b)	1620(s)	1720(s) 1590(s)	1390(s)	1030(s)	420(w)	380(w)
11.	—	—	3300(b)	1620(s)	1710(s) 1590(s)	1390(s)	1030(s)	410(w)	370(w)
12.	—	—	3300(b)	1620(s)	1710(s) 1590(s)	1390(s)	1030(s)	450(w)	400(w)

*As in Table 1.
All values are in cm^{-1} .

which are lower than those expected for high spin octahedral cobalt(II) complexes (4.7-5.2 B.M.). This may be attributed to incomplete quenching of the orbital contribution to the magnetic moment⁴.

The three absorption bands obtained in the electronic spectra of these complexes corresponding

to three spin allowed d-d transitions are given in Table 3. The reflectance spectra also gave the same bands indicating thereby no dissociation of the complexes in solution. These bands are generally located near 8000, 17000 and 20500 cm^{-1} , which is characteristic of octahedral complexes of

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex no.*	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F_1)$	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(F_2)$	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_2)	10Dq	B	β	ν_2/ν_1	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
1.	8200	16200	21000	9382.89	932.19	0.960	1.97	4.46
2.	8240	16500	20500	9405.69	895.04	0.921	2.00	4.50
3.	8050	16200	20400	9203.16	900.21	0.927	2.01	4.55
4.	8040	16200	21000	9214.74	942.31	0.970	2.01	4.59
5.	8000	16500	20400	9150.77	903.38	0.930	2.06	4.57
6.	8000	15900	20800	9165.46	931.03	0.958	1.98	4.50
7.	8350	16600	20800	9532.08	908.85	0.935	1.98	4.50
8.	8240	16500	20500	9405.69	895.04	0.921	2.00	4.48
9.	8190	17200	21000	9372.40	932.82	0.960	2.10	4.50
10.	8190	17200	21000	9372.40	932.82	0.960	2.10	4.58
11.	8000	16500	19800	9127.69	861.84	0.887	2.06	4.52
12.	8000	17000	21000	9172.61	944.84	0.973	2.12	4.57

*As in Table 1.

cobalt(II)⁵⁻⁷. Ligand field splitting energy (10Dq) and Racah interelectronic repulsion parameter (B) were calculated using the following equations.

$$10Dq = \frac{1}{2}[(2\nu_2 - \nu_3) + (\nu_2^2 + \nu_1\nu_3 - \nu_1^2)^{1/2}]$$

$$15B = (\nu_3 - 2\nu_1 + 10Dq).$$

The values of 10Dq, B and β (nephelauxetic ratio) are given in Table 3. Lever⁸ suggested for octahedral cobalt(II) complexes that ν_3 should be approximately twice but not greater than 2.2 that of ν_1 transition. Ferguson *et al.*^{9,11} and Holmas and McCluer¹⁰ have calculated the ratio ν_3/ν_1 to be 1.97, 2.02 and 2.07 for the aquo, chloro and bromo complexes of Co(II). In our case the values of ν_3/ν_1 were found in the range 1.97-2.10.

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